

Complexes of Uranium(IV) and Thorium(IV) with Thiophene-2-Carboxylic Acid

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Stable chelates of uranium(IV) and thorium(IV) of the formulae, U_2Cl_2 , $U(OAc)_2L_2$ and $Th(OAc)L_3$ (LH = thiophene-2-carboxylic acid) have been synthesised from $U(OAc)_4$ or $Th(OAc)_4$. Magnetic susceptibility, IR and reflectance spectra of U(IV) complexes and IR of Th(IV) complex indicate eight coordination for U(IV) in these chelates.

Interaction between Cu(II) and sulphur of thiophene-2-carboxylic acid has been shown in solution.¹

However, no solid complex of thiophene-2-carboxylic acid has been reported so far. In the present work stable chelates of uranium(IV) and thorium(IV) with thiophene-2-carboxylic acid have been prepared and characterised on the basis of IR, electronic and magnetic susceptibility data.

Experimental

U(IV) and Th(IV) acetates were prepared as reported in literature^{2,3}. Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (Kochlight) was used as such. Ethanol and benzene were purified and dried by usual methods and benzene was stored over sodium.

Bis(thiophene-2-carboxylato) oxouranium(IV) (Chelate-I). Uranium(IV) acetate (0.61 g.) in water was mixed with thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (0.67 g.) in ethanol (40 ml). Green coloured complex got precipitated which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 . Found: U, 45.10; C, 24.60; H, 1.43; S, 11.90%. Calc. for: $U(C_4H_3SCOO)_2$, U, 46.85; C, 23.60; H, 1.20; S, 12.60%. Reflectance spectra bands occur at 1950 sh, 1620sh, 1490vs, 1110vs, 840b, 670vs, 550sh, 480sh nm.

Diacetatobis(thiophene-2-carboxylato)uranium(IV) (Chelate-II). Uranium tetracetate (0.94g.) and thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (0.51g.) were refluxed in benzene (50 ml) for 8 hr. Green coloured complex was filtered, washed with benzene and dried *in vacuo*. Found: U, 39.03; C, 25.40; H, 2.18; S, 10.20%. Calc. for: $U(CH_3COO)_2(C_4H_3SCOO)_2$, U, 39.46, C, 27.54; H, 1.97; S, 10.50%. Reflectance spectra bands occur at 1925sh, 1520s, 1430sh, 1125vs, 880s, 670vs, 655sh, 620sh, 550s, 485s, 435s nm.

Acetatotris(thiophene-2-carboxylato)thorium(IV) (Chelate-III). Thorium(IV) acetate (0.1 g.) was

suspended in ethanol (10 ml). Thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (0.54 g.) dissolved in ethanol was added to the above suspension. On refluxing the contents for 2 hr., white coloured complex separated out which was washed with dry ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Found: Th, 34.09%. Calc. for: $Th(CH_3COO)(C_4H_3SCOO)_3$, Th, 34.68%.

Uranium and thorium were estimated as follows: Uranium(IV) or thorium(IV) complex (~0.1 g.) was weighed directly into silica crucible. It was ignited to constant weight at ~850° and weighed as U_3O_8 or ThO_2 respectively.

IR spectra (nujol) of U(IV) chelates were recorded on Unicam SP-1200 Spectrophotometer. IR Spectra (nujol) of Th(IV) chelate and ligand were recorded on Specord-71 IR Spectrophotometer. Diffuse reflectance spectra of U(IV) chelates were recorded on Unicam SP-700 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities of the U(IV) chelates were measured at room temperature on Gouy balance.

Results and Discussion

The chelates are stable at room temperature and do not melt upto 300° but decompose at higher temperature giving U_3O_8 and ThO_2 at ~600° and ~850° respectively. The chelates are, however, insoluble in common organic solvents, indicating polymeric nature for these complexes.

IR spectra (nujol) of the ligand thiophene-2-carboxylic acid and its chelates have been recorded. The band at 1660 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is right in the unconjugated C=C region and is probably not a Carboxylate frequency at all⁴. The bands at 1525, 1435 and 1400 cm^{-1} in the ligand [$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$] shift to 1540, 1510 and 1390 cm^{-1} in chelate I; 1540, 1440 and 1400 cm^{-1} in chelate II and 1520, 1420 and 1390 cm^{-1} in

chelate III which indicate coordination through carboxylic group⁵. ν_{asym} (OCO) and ν_{sym} (OCO) are consistent with normal bridging e.g. as in the tetraacetates. A strong band at 1105 cm^{-1} [$\nu(\text{c}\cdots\cdots\text{s})$] shifts to 1130, 1135 and 1125 cm^{-1} in chelates (I) to (III) respectively which indicates that sulphur atom of the ligand coordinates to U(IV) and Th(IV) respectively⁶. The chelate I is polymeric with

O—U—O—U...or U U linkages. There is no

evidence in IR spectrum for UO^{2+} entity. The strong bands at 770 and 725 cm^{-1} are probably due to antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations of a unit O—U—O^{5,7}.

The reflectance spectra of the chelates I and II are comparable with the eight coordinated U(IV) complexes⁸⁻¹⁰. This may suggest the same coordination number for chelates I and II.

The μ_{eff} of chelates (I) and (II) are 1.40 and 2.63 B. M. respectively. The μ_{eff} of 2.63 B.M. for

the chelate (II) is comparable to that reported where uranium (IV) is eight coordinated⁸⁻¹⁰. very low μ_{eff} of 1.40 B.M. for the chelate (I) may be due to metal-metal interaction involving oxygen bridging, also evidenced from IR spectra.

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